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Current Municipal Spending on Culture in the Italian Regions During the Period 2010-2020

It decreased on average by 22.61% between 2010 and 2020

Istat calculates the value of municipalities' current spending on culture. The variable is defined as the value of accrual payments for the protection and valorisation of cultural assets and activities, in euros per capita. The data refers to the Italian regions between 2010 and 2020.

Ranking of the Italian regions by value of the current expenditure of the municipalities for culture in the Italian regions in 2020. Trentino Alto Adige is in first place for the value of the current expenditure of the municipalities for culture in 2020 with a value equal to 46.9 units, followed by Friuli Venezia Giulia with 32.5 units, and by Emilia Romagna with an amount of 31.1 units. In the middle of the table are Lombardy with a value of 20.1 units, followed by Lazio with a value of 19.9 units and Veneto with an amount of 19.2 units. Molise closes the ranking with a value of 5.3 units, followed by Calabria with an amount of 5.1 units and Campania with 2.7 units.

Ranking of the Italian regions by value of the percentage change in the current expenditure of municipalities for culture in the Italian regions between 2010 and 2020. Sardinia is in first place by value of the percentage changes with an amount equal to -5.09% corresponding to a variation from an amount of 27.5 units up to a value of 26.1 units between 2010 and 2020. Friuli Venezia Giulia follows with a variation equal to -14.25% corresponding to a variation from an amount of 37, 9 units up to 32.5 units between 2010 and 2020. Veneto follows with a value equal to -14.67% corresponding to a variation from an amount of 22.5 units up to a value of 19.2 units. In the middle of the table are Lombardy with an amount equal to -19.28% corresponding to a variation from an amount of 24.9 units up to a value of 20.1 units. Marche follows with a variation corresponding to a reduction of -20.39% corresponding to an amount from 25.5 up to a value of 20.3 units. Lazio follows with a value equal to -30.18% corresponding to an amount from 28.5 units up to a value of 19.9 units. Molise closes the ranking with an amount equal to -53.1% corresponding to a variation from an amount of 11.3 units up to a value of 5.3 units. Calabria follows with an amount equal to -54.05% corresponding to a variation from an amount of 11.1 units up to a value of 5.1 units. Campania closes the ranking with an amount equal to -61.97% corresponding to a variation from an amount of 7.1 units up to a value of 2.7 units. On average, the value of spending on culture by municipalities in the Italian regions decreased by 22.61% between 2010 and 2022.

The current expenditure of municipalities for culture in the Italian macro-regions between 2010 and 2020. The value of the current expenditure of municipalities for culture decreased in all Italian macro-regions between 2010 and 2020, i.e.: South with a -50.00%, Southern Italy with -38.26%, Center with -25.09%, Islands with -22.01%, North-West with -17.87%, North with -16.12%, North-East with -

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15.29%. We can note that the value of the municipalities' current expenditure on culture, although it has decreased in all the Italian macro-regions, still presents important differences between the South and the Centre-North. In fact, the current expenditure of municipalities for culture in the South is 78.14% lower than in the Centre, 75.65% lower than in the North-West, 79.48% lower than in the North, -83.03% lower than in the North East. Therefore, even in the general reduction in current spending by municipalities on culture in the Italian macro-regions, the presence of a North-South gap is highlighted which reaches up to 83.03% when comparing the South with the North-East.

Clustering with k-Means algorithm optimized with the Silhouette coefficient. Below we present a clustering with k-Means algorithm optimized with the Silhouette coefficient. The Valle d'Aosta region was excluded from the clustering analysis due to insufficient data. The analysis highlights the presence of four clusters as indicated below:

- Cluster 1: Puglia, Calabria, Molise, Abruzzo, Sicily, Basilicata, Campania;
- Cluster 2: Marche, Lombardy, Veneto, Umbria, Lazio, Piedmont, Liguria, Sardinia;
- Cluster 3: Emilia Romagna, Friuli Venezia Giulia, Tuscany;
- Cluster 4: Trentino-Alto Adige.

Looking at the ordering of the clusters based on the average value of the municipalities' current expenditure on culture we can notice the following structure: C4>C3>C2>C1. That is, the value of the municipalities' current spending on culture tends to be high in the center and north and low in the south of Italy. We note that the last cluster in terms of value of municipal spending on culture, i.e. cluster 1, is made up of almost all the southern regions with the sole exception of Sardinia which instead participates in cluster 2, i.e. the penultimate cluster. Particularly evident is the structure of Cluster 4-C4, composed exclusively of Trentino Alto Adige, which has a very high level of municipal spending on culture compared to the other clusters. That is, if on the one hand in Trentino Alto Adige the current municipal expenditure for culture varies between around 50 euros per capita in the observation period, on the other hand, for the regions of Cluster 2, i.e. the last cluster, the expenditure municipal per capita for culture is around 10-12 euros.

Conclusions. The analysis carried out shows that current municipal spending on culture decreased in all Italian regions and macro-regions in the observation period, i.e. between 2010 and 2022. However, even in this generalized reduction, a geographical gap between the Center and the -North and South Italy. In fact, the southern regions have very low levels of municipal current spending on culture compared to the corresponding values of the northern regions. From a strictly quantitative point of view, the value of municipal per capita spending on culture in 2020 is equal to 7.1 euros in the South compared to 21.5 euros in Central Italy, 27.70 euros in the North-East, 19.3 euros from the North-West. The North-East is therefore the Italian macro-region that reaches the highest levels of spending on culture at municipal level. However, it is necessary to consider that the historical series analyzed stops at 2020 and does not take into consideration the effects of Covid-19. It is in fact very likely that the value of current municipal spending on culture decreased even more during Covid and then increased between 2022 and 2023. In general we can note that the value of spending on culture appears to be very low in absolute terms. In fact, if we consider that many Italian cities welcome tourists, we understand that this value should increase in the medium-long term instead of decreasing. It is certainly necessary to consider that the vast majority of Italian municipalities are in terrible budgetary conditions. Some municipalities are even technically bankrupt. Others require continuous financial interventions from the state or regions. In reality, the budget policies that can be implemented at the local level are truly low profile. It follows that municipalities cut current spending where they can. And one of the first spending items to be cut is culture. So the paradox remains. Italy

is a country that attracts tens of millions of tourists from abroad for its culture and historical heritage and yet reduces investment at municipal level. Many activities carried out in municipalities are actually financed by regional bodies and ministries. Especially the most relevant events that have the ability to attract tourists and visitors from other regions or abroad. The role of the private for-profit sector and foundations in promoting local culture has yet to be defined. In fact, the reduction in current municipal spending on culture could be more than compensated by regional spending in the municipalities and by private intervention. Even if to get private individuals to intervene, both for profit and non-profit, it is necessary to establish regulations and initiate a public-private governance which on the one hand avoids private speculation and on the other hand offers fair recognition in terms of brand value and market share to investors.

Declarations

Data Availability Statement. The data presented in this study are available on request from the corresponding author.

Funding. The author received no financial support for the research, authorship, and/or publication of this article.

Declaration of Competing Interest. The author declares that there is no conflict of interests regarding the publication of this manuscript. In addition, the ethical issues, including plagiarism, informed consent, misconduct, data fabrication and/or falsification, double publication.

Acknowledgements. I am grateful to the teaching staff of the LUM University “Giuseppe Degennaro” and to the management of the LUM Enterprise s.r.l. for the constant inspiration to continue our scientific research work undeterred.

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Appendix

